

PHONETIC COMPETENCE IN CONDITIONS OF ARTIFICIAL MULTILINGUALISM

**Namozova Dilnoza Berdimurotovna,
Rashidova Munavvar Xaydarovna**

University of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan, senior teachers at the
Department of Languages

***Annotation.** The article explores the features of teaching the pronunciation part of speech in the conditions of contact of three or more languages. These conditions are referred to as artificial multilingualism. The goal of teaching phonetics in artificial multilingualism, as well as in teaching the first foreign language, is to form phonetic competence, which includes specific skills (auditory and pronunciation), knowledge and skills. Special attention is paid to the interaction of phonetic skills of contacting languages. The result of this interaction is phonetic interference.*

***Key words:** phonological signs, articulatory base, foreign language accent, phonetic skill, phonetic competence, artificial multilingualism, pronunciation.*

In the conditions of linguistic lyceums, linguistic universities and faculties, in the study of foreign languages, a situation of artificial multilingualism develops, by which we mean proficiency in two or more foreign languages as a result of purposeful learning. This type of multilingualism is characterized by “asymmetric communicative competence in relation to languages in contact and the controlled nature of its formation”.

Within the framework of the competence-based approach, the goal of teaching a foreign language (first, second, etc.) is communicative competence, which is the basis for the development of multilingual competence. Multilingual competence should be understood as a network of complex relationships of knowledge and linguistic experience that a person acquires gradually and in stages. An integral component responsible for the competent design of an utterance is linguistic competence, consisting of phonetic, lexical, and grammatical.

Phonetic competence includes phonetic skills, knowledge and ability to perceive and reproduce the following elements:

- phonemes and their implementation in a specific context (allophones);
- phonetic signs that distinguish some phonemes from others (sonority, nasality, labialization, etc.);

- prosody; the phenomena of assimilation at the moment of articulation, reduction of unstressed vowels, phrasal stress and rhythm; intonation, etc.

The importance of the pronunciation side of speech is due to its entry into all types of speech activity. For example, as a component of speaking, pronunciation can make words easier or more difficult for the listener to recognize. The communicative significance of the pronunciation side of speaking is to give clarity to the oral text. In listening, the pronunciation side of speech is directly involved in the process of perception. If the student perceives the spoken text incorrectly, he has difficulties in identifying, understanding and interpreting the text, i.e. insufficient level of phonetic competence makes it difficult to understand speech by ear.

In the field of phonetics, the influence of the native language on the studied foreign language is more pronounced than at other levels of the language. Difficulties in mastering the sounds of a foreign language are explained by the interference of the native language.

O. A. Yamshchikova understands phonetic interference as “violation (distortion) of the secondary and subsequent language system and its norms as a result of interaction in the speaker’s mind of phonetic systems and pronunciation systems of two or more languages”. There is an interference of auditory and pronunciation skills formed on the basis of interacting systems. Pronunciation is the most automated area of the language. In mastering pronunciation, skill plays a decisive role. Phonetic skills provide the ability to correctly perceive the audible sounds of foreign language speech and reproduce them adequately to the existing norm.

The depth and amount of interference can vary. The result of phonetic interference is a foreign language accent, which is characterized as "substitution of unknown sounds and unusual combinations of sounds with their own familiar ones and rethinking of words with their morphological composition and their meanings according to the skills of their language".

Classical phonological models are based on the concept of "phonological sieve" by N.S. Trubetskoy. N.S. Trubetskoy compared the phonological system of language to a sieve through which everything that is heard is sifted. When an individual hears speech in another language, he involuntarily applies the phonological filter of his native language to analyze what he heard. Due to the fact that the perception filter is not adapted to the new language, numerous errors and misunderstandings arise. The presence of the so-called foreign accent N.S. Trubetskoy connected not with the fact that the individual cannot pronounce a certain sound, but rather with the fact that he does not distinguish, interpret incorrectly and does not correct this sound.

The sounds of a foreign language are assimilated with the phonological categories of the native language. The named erroneous interpretation is due to the difference in the phonological structures of the native and foreign languages. Hence the need to develop auditory differential sensitivity and train phonemic hearing.

W. Weinreich distinguishes the following types of phonetic interference:

1) insufficient differentiation - mixing of two phonemes of the secondary system, as a result of which similar units of the primary do not differ as special phonemes;

2) excessive differentiation - the imposition of phonemic differences of the primary system on the sounds of the secondary, which are a variant of one phoneme;

3) misinterpretation - distinguishing phonemes of the secondary system according to features that are relevant for the primary system, and for the secondary they are secondary or redundant;

4) substitution - the substitution of units of the secondary system with units of the primary.

From the above, an important methodological conclusion follows: at the stage of presenting a new sound, it is necessary to make a clear differentiation, to achieve correct interpretation, not being limited to imitation of the sound.

To master the phonetic base of the language being studied, it is necessary, first of all, to master the articulatory structure typical for the native speakers of this language. The articulatory mode means the habitual position of the organs of speech at the moment when the speaker does not perform articulatory movements.

Acquaintance with the way of speech organs is a kind of "tuning" to a certain way of pronunciation. Therefore, we consider it expedient to devote the very first lesson on a new language to the formation of a holistic idea of its phonetic system.

Since pronunciation skills are formed on the basis of the articulatory base of the language, it is necessary to consider the features of the articulatory bases of all contacting languages in order to identify potentially complex phonetic elements, explain and remove existing difficulties. The articulatory base is understood as "a set of movements and positions of the pronunciation organs that are customary for a given language, the formation of which depends on the phonemic system of the language and, which is especially important, on the differential features used in it".

Immersion in a new language occurs from the first lesson. The features of the articulatory base of the corresponding language can be presented using the example of the alphabet. Acquaintance with the articulatory base of a new language occurs in the following sequence.

1. Each letter is spelled out and explained. Writing letters and paying attention to the differences are very important, since the developed skill of writing letters consistently interferes.

2. When explaining the pronunciation of each letter with transcription, comparisons of the studied language with the native and first (native, first and second) foreign languages are made when necessary.

For clarity, you can use articulation schemes. Thus, there is an acquaintance with almost all the features of the articulatory base in practice.

Having disassembled the alphabet, students receive memorization as homework. In the next lesson, the alphabet is checked and corrected. Further, the theoretical material on the features of the articulatory base is analyzed. Since in practice, students have already become familiar with the new articulatory base, the theoretical material is perceived by them in a natural way.

REFERENCES:

1. Namozova D.B. Phonetic competence development. – Ўзбекистонда миллий тадқиқотлар. Даврий анжуманлар: 10-қисм Тошкент, январь 2022. p.56
2. Namozova Dilnoza Berdimurotovna. 2021. Difficulties cadets face while practicing listening and the ways of eliminating them. International Journal of Research and Development. Volume 6. Issue 5. pp.36-38
3. Namozova Dilnoza Berdimurotovna. 2021. Peculiarities of phonetic competence development in conditions of artificial multilingualism. Инновации в педагогике и психологии. Номер 4, Выпуск 1. С.82-86.
4. Namozova Dilnoza Berdimurotovna. 2022. Development of phonetic competence. Science and education. 3 (9) pp. 413-415
5. Namozova Dilnoza Berdimurotovna. 2023. Phonetic competence. Science and education. 4(2) pp.1676-1679
6. Rashidova Munavvar Xaydarovna. Recommendations on the use of scaffolding technology in English classes. Science and education. 2022. Volume 3. Issue 9. pp. 459-461.
7. Rashidova Munavvar Xaydarovna, Namozova Dilnoza Berdimurotovna. Teaching technical subjects through English. Ўзбекистонда миллий тадқиқотлар: даврий анжуманлар: 10-қисм. 32-б.
8. Rashidova Munavvar Xaydarovna, Namozova Dilnoza Berdimurotovna. 2021. Effective methods of teaching. Materials of the republican 33-multidisciplinary online distance conference on “Scientific and practical research in Uzbekistan”. Part-10. pp. 23-24.

9. Utenbaeva, G. M. "The importance of listening skills in teaching Russian language to the cadets of military institute." EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD), INDIA SJIF Impact Factor 6: 18-21.
10. Утенбаева, Гульжазира Мухтаровна, and ООРЯ ВБОУ. "РУЗ С Использованием инновационных педагогических технологий с целью совершенствования их стратегической компетенции." (2021).
11. Наркулова И. Р. К. Профессионально-ориентированное обучение русскому языку курсантов юридического профиля на основе интерактивной программы //Science and Education. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 1348-1352.
12. Закирова А. О., Наркулова И. Р. К. Роль русского языка в работе сотрудников органов внутренних дел //Science and Education. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 1. – С. 737-740.
13. Булычёва М. Ф. Учебные экскурсии для формирования лингвокультурологической компетенции курсантов //Science and Education. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 1. – С. 808-813.
14. Булычёва М. Ф. Применение на начальном этапе различных видов наглядности //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 12. – С. 751-758.